

A STUDY TO ASSESS THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SELF INSTRUCTIONAL MODULES FOR TEACHERS IN MANAGEMENT OF BEHAVIOURAL PROBLEMS IN SCHOOL CHILDREN IN SELECTED RURAL AREA

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Abstract

Background: A child's mental health is fundamental to their ability to live in harmony in a world that is always changing. Child's health is the corner stone of national progress. In India, Children below 16 years of age constitute over 40% of its population, Community studies on emotional/ behavioural disorders in children and adolescents conducted in India have yielded disparate point prevalence estimates (2.6% to 35.6%). Teachers are the persons who are caring the school going children for a long time with them in schools when comparing to their parents. So school teachers should have adequate knowledge regarding early identification of behavioral problems of school children which will promote the behavioral status of the children. **objective:** To assess the pretest and post test level of knowledge on management of behavioural problems in school children among school teachers. To assess the effectiveness of self instructional modules for teachers in the management of behavioural problems in school children. To associate the post test level of knowledge on management of behavioural problems in school children among school teachers with their selected demographic variables. **Methodology:** Research approach: quantitative approach, quasi experimental research design was used for 60 samples by non-probability convenient sampling technique method. **Result:** on comparing the pre test and post test knowledge among the teacher ,in pretest, 22(73.33%) of teachers had inadequate knowledge and 8(26.67%) of teachers had moderately adequate knowledge and in the post test after then intervention, 21(70%)of teachers had adequate knowledge and 9(30%) of teachers had moderately adequate knowledge in the experimental group.

Keywords: Effectiveness, Self-Instructional Module, Teachers, Behavioral problems, School Children.

INTRODUCTION

It is possible for young individuals to experience genuine, difficult, and expensive mental, emotional, and behavioral issues. These problems often can lead to development of disorders if neglected which are the sources of stress for children and their families, schools and communities (**According to WHO 1977**) Although it is difficult to get accurate estimates of child mental disorders, the few available epidemiological data indicate that 12-51%; with the average around 29% of the world's children suffer from emotional and other mental problems that warrant mental health treatment[1] Out of this group, 6-9% is seriously emotionally disturbed children who need intensive psychiatric care[2] In addition, there are increasing number of children who are at-risk and require care as well as secondary preventive services. According to recent data, emotional and behavioral issues frequently result in subpar academic performance and school dropout. This wastes educational resources and seriously impairs the economic and social potential of such children[3] The behavioural

problems such as quarrelling, using abusive language, delinquent behaviour are visible in school children in general. A child may have more than one disorder ranging from mild to severe[4] In Assam, a cross sectional study on school students shows prevalence rate of various behavioural problems ranged from 7.90 to 16.78%. Anxiety problem was highest among school students[5] Children spent nearly 200 days each year in the school. Thus, a significant amount of the child's day and week are spent at school. So it is the primary responsibility of the school, not only to build up their intellectual capacity and knowledge but also to develop their physical and mental health[6] "A successful teacher emphasizes the role of guide, facilitator, leader, manager, and evaluator," stated Dr. Sarvepalli Radhakrishnan. Among the essential and vital roles in school health services is that of the teacher. There is no replacement for the teacher's invaluable involvement in child care. Instructors can assist students in gaining health information and comprehension, cultivating positive attitudes, and creating healthy practices that will enhance both their individual and community health. [7] A teacher is a person who provides students with direct classroom teaching, or classroom-type teaching in a non classroom setting. Teachers have an impact on how a person develops their personality. One of a teacher's most crucial roles is to listen to their students' difficulties. Early identification and intervention for children with behavioral issues can lower treatment expenses and enhance the quality of life for those kids. Teachers are the persons who are caring Compared to their parents, school-age children attend schools for a longer period of time with them. So school teachers should have adequate knowledge regarding early identification of behavioral problems of school children which will promote the behavioral status of the children[8] A child is an important asset to the family, society and nation. It is a priceless gift with endless possibilities.. The child can be a best resource for nation if developed and utilized well. Good physical and mental health is an essential component of human resource development that cannot be overlooked. Therefore, enhancing health, particularly in children, will be an affordable means of advancing national development. It is only the healthy that can grow into the healthy citizen. Being the greatest assets, they provide the foundation for the future health and strength of the nation. A child is an invaluable resource for the household, neighborhood, and nation. It is a priceless gift with endless possibilities. If a child is raised and used properly, they can be the greatest resource for their country. Good physical and mental health is an essential component of human resource development that cannot be overlooked. Therefore, enhancing health, particularly in children, will be an affordable means of advancing national development. It is only the healthy that can grow into the healthy citizen. They are the most valuable resources since they provide the groundwork for the country's continued prosperity and health. Furthermore, it is important to remember that every person has the inherent right to life, including the right to develop to the fullest extent possible. [9] So the current study aimed to assess the effectiveness of self instructional modules for teachers in the management of behavioural problems in school children and To associate the post test level of knowledge on management of behavioural problems in school children among school teachers with their selected demographic.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study design: A Quantitative approach with quasi experimental design was adopted for the study. **Study Setting:** This study was conducted at selected schools in rural area ,after obtaining ethical clearance from the Institutional Ethical Committee (IEC)

of Saveetha Medical College And Hospitals (SIMATS) and a formal permission from presidents of selected rural areas. **Study Participants:** A total 60 school teachers working in the selected schools in selected rural area who fulfils and meets the inclusion criteria were recruited as study participants who were not willing to participate were excluded. The purpose of the study was explained in depth by the investigator to each of the study participants and a written informed consent was obtained from them. **Sampling Techniques:** A total of 60 school teachers were recruited based on the inclusion criteria by using non-probability convenient sampling technique. All the 60 samples were randomly assigned to either the intervention or the placebo group by using lottery methods. 30 samples were selected for experimental group, 30 sample were selected for control group. A self structured questionnaire method was used to gather the demographic data .The collected data was summarized, and tabulated in a Microsoft office excel and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics.

Intervention protocol:

The pretest level of knowledge was assessed by using the structured knowledge questionnaire on 1st day. Then the self instructional module on knowledge on management of behavioural problems was administered for 25 to 30 minutes every day among the school teachers and the post test was done on the 7th day.

RESULT

Demographic Characteristics

Among 60 study participants, with regards most of the teachers, 14(46.7%) in the experimental and 13(43.3%) in the control group were aged between 26 – 31 years, 21(70%) in the experimental and 22(73.3%) in the control group were female, 17(56.7%) in the experimental and 16(53.3%) in the control group had B.Ed as qualification, 21(70%) in the experimental and 22(73.3%) in the control group had 5 – 10 years of experience, 27(90%) in the experimental and 25(83.3%) in the control group were unmarried, 30(100%) in the experimental and control group had no child psychology in curriculum and not attended any Inservice education on management of behavioural problem of learning and 24(80%) in the experimental and 22(73.3%) in the control group had not ever taught children with behavioural problems.

ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE ON MANAGEMENT OF BEHAVIOURAL PROBLEMS IN SCHOOL CHILDREN IN THE EXPERIMENTAL GROUP.

Table 1: Frequency and percentage distribution of pretest and post test level of knowledge on management of behavioural problems in school children in the experimental group. N = 30

Level of Knowledge	Pretest		Post Test	
	No.	%	No.	%
Inadequate (≤50%)	22	73.33	-	-
Moderately Adequate (51 – 75%)	8	26.67	9	30.0
Adequate (>75%)	-	-	21	70.0

The table 1 shows that in the pretest, 22(73.33%) had inadequate knowledge and 8(26.67%) had moderately adequate knowledge and in the post test after then intervention, 21(70%) had adequate knowledge and 9(30%) had moderately adequate knowledge in the experimental group.

Figure 1: Percentage distribution of pretest and post test level of knowledge on management of behavioural problems in school children in the experimental group

The present study finding was supported by quasi experimental study conducted by **Bhanwara P. [2011]** Among 60 school teachers Majority (93.34%) of the school teachers in pre-test of the experimental had an average knowledge score (8-14). Whereas in post-test a majority 75% of the school teachers had a good knowledge score (15-20). on management of behavioural problems in school children. [10]

EFFECTIVENESS OF SELF INSTRUCTIONAL MODULE FOR TEACHERS IN MANAGEMENT OF BEHAVIOURAL PROBLEMS AMONG SCHOOL CHILDREN.

Table 2: Comparison of pretest and post test knowledge scores of teachers on management of behavioural problems among schoolchildren within and between the experimental and control group. N = 60(30+30)

Knowledge	Experimental		Control		Mean Difference score	Student Independent 't' test & p-value
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D		
Pretest	4.46	1.40	4.53	1.47	0.07	t = 0.179 p=0.859, N.S
Post test	8.23	1.25	4.63	1.47	3.60	t = 10.202 p=0.0001, S***
Mean Difference Score	3.77		0.10		***p<0.001 S – Significant N.S – Not Significant	
Paired "t" test & p-value	t = 25.246 p=0.0001 S***		t = 1.795 p=0.083, N.S			

The table 2 depicts that the pretest mean score of knowledge experimental group was 4.46 ± 1.40 and post test mean score was 4.53 ± 1.47 . The mean difference score was 3.77. The calculated student paired 't' test value of $t=25.246$ was statistically significant at $p<0.001$ level. This clearly shows that self instructional module administered to the teachers was found to be effective in improving the level of knowledge in the post test.

The table 2 depicts that the pretest mean score of knowledge in the control group was 4.53 ± 1.47 and post test mean score was 4.63 ± 1.47 . The mean difference score was

0.10. The calculated student paired 't' test value of $t=1.795$ was not statistically significant. This clearly shows that there was no significant difference between the pretest and post test knowledge scores among the teachers.

The calculated student independent 't' test value of $t=0.179$ in the pretest was not statistically significant at $p<0.05$ level. This clearly shows that there was no statistically difference was observed in the pretest level of knowledge between the groups.

The table 2 depicts that the calculated student independent 't' test value of $t=10.202$ was statistically significant at $p<0.001$ level. This clearly shows that self instructional module administered to the teachers was found to be effective in improving the level of knowledge in the post test than the teachers in the control group who had been administered with normal daily routines.

The current study was supported by study conducted by **Jitendra Chicholkar[2022]** The mean of post-test knowledge scores was 26.6 which is significantly higher than mean of pre-test knowledge scores of 12.4. Standard deviation of post-test score and pre-test score is 9.4 and 13.3 respectively. The computed paired "t" value (18.67, $df=99$ at the level of $P= 0.05$) is greater than table value (1.66) which represents significant gain in knowledge. [11]

ASSOCIATION OF POST TEST LEVEL OF BEHAVIOURAL PROBLEMS IN SCHOOL CHILDREN WITH SELECTED DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES. T

The demographic variable educational qualification ($\chi^2=6.022$, $p = 0.049$) had shown statistically significant association with post test level of knowledge of teachers on management of behavioural problems in school children at $p<0.05$ level and the other demographic variables had not shown statistically significant association with post test level of knowledge of teachers on management of behavioural problems in school children.

The current study was supported by study conducted by **Jitendra Chicholkar[2022]** among 100 school teachers Association between the pre test knowledge score with the selected demographic variables.²: There will be significant association between the pre test knowledge score and selected demographic variables at the level of $P\leq 0.05$. is accepted as there is significant association between pretest knowledge score and selected demographic variables like educational qualification, years of experience, child psychology in syllabus and attended in-service education.(11)

CONCLUSION

According to the study, school teachers' pre-test understanding of learning disabilities was low, but their post-test knowledge had significantly increased. Thus the study results revealed that self-instructional module is an effective instructional method to improve the knowledge level of primary school teachers regarding learning disabilities.

Limitations of The Present Study

Generalization will be better if large sample included. The study limited to one week.

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Conflict of Interest

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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